

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF ACOUSTIC MODES OF A DEPTH VARIABLE HELMHOLTZ RESONATOR FOR LOW TO HIGH SUBSONIC FLOW SPEEDS

Steffen Hammer
KTH Royal Institute
of Technology
Stockholm, Sweden

Jens Fridh
KTH Royal Institute of
Technology
Stockholm, Sweden

Mattias Billson
GKN Aerospace
Sweden
Trollhättan, Sweden

ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the resonance behavior of a Helmholtz resonator with an adjustable depth for low to high subsonic flow speeds. A special focus is the interaction of the Helmholtz resonator with Rossiter modes and possible prediction methods for amplified resonances due to their interaction. Measurements have been performed for a variation of L/D ratios in the range of 2 to 0.25 for flow speeds of Mach 0.3 to 0.8. Rossiter, Helmholtz and Quarter wavelength models are used for comparison. The experimental analysis of several unsteady pressure transducers around the cavity shows that theoretical prediction models of the acoustical characteristics only match up to intermediate subsonic flow speeds of Mach 0.6. For these models the highest amplitudes are measured for L/D ratios below 0.6. At high subsonic flows the measurement data deviated from the used theoretical models and requires additional correlation models.

Keywords: Aeroacoustics, Helmholtz, Rossiter

NOMENCLATURE

A_{opening}	Area of the cavity opening [m ²]
γ	Specific heat ratio
b	Constant defined by Rossiter
c	Speed of sound [m/s]
δ_r	Correction factor by Chanaud [m]
l_{eff}	Effective geometric length [m]
l_{neck}	Neck length of the cavity [m]
f	Frequency [Hz]
f_{half}	Half wavelength frequency [Hz]
f_{Helm}	Helmholtz frequency [Hz]
f_{quarter}	Quarter wavelength frequency [Hz]
$p_{s,\text{window}}$	Static pressure at side window [kPa]
$p_{\text{tot,settling}}$	Total pressure at settling chamber [kPa]
D	Cavity depth [m]
K	Constant defined by Rossiter

L	Cavity opening length [m]
LE	Cavity leading edge
M	Mach number
R	Radius in corners of cavity volume [m]
T	Baseplate thickness [m]
TE	Cavity trailing edge
U	Flow speed [m/s]
V	Cavity Volume [m ³]
W	Cavity width [m]
FFT	Fast Fourier Transformation
PSD	Power Spectral Density [kPa ² /Hz]

1. INTRODUCTION

The demand in turbomachinery for good numerical tools in the design of ever more efficient and high performing aero engines is uninterrupted. In recent times acoustic resonances in the engines have led to grounding and redesign of components [1]. For example, Aleksentsev et al. showed the existence of acoustic resonances in bleed systems of the Russian PS-90-A engine [2]. The bleed system of an engine represents a complicated shaped Helmholtz resonator.

Flow over the opening of a Helmholtz resonator have been studied in a wide range of applications from car sunroofs [3, 4, 5], gas pipelines [6] and liners aerospace application [7]. The common usage of these resonators is noise dampening [8], which means the effects of the resonator are of desire to the designer. However, the noise generation of the cavity can be unintended as in an airplane landing gear opening [9] or the above mentioned bleed system where it can lead to flow excited resonance.

An experimental database was started by studying the acoustic behavior of an open box cavity for low to high subsonic speeds by Hammer et al. [10] in order to deepen the knowledge of cavity resonance. The results allowed to identify Rossiter modes in accordance to theoretical predictions. Furthermore, mode-shifting behavior and other acoustic resonances based on wavelength models were observed.

The geometry of bleed cavities is not straight forward and does not follow simple geometric shapes. Therefore more experimental data is required. By choosing a Helmholtz resonator design the experimental complexity is increased from the previous studies with a simple open box cavity [10] but still simple enough to follow theoretical models.

Ma et al. [11] investigated the flow excitation of a Helmholtz resonator numerically and experimentally for very low subsonic flows ($M < 0.13$). They were able to describe the interaction of the flow and the resonator.

In this context, this paper evaluates resonance behavior of a Helmholtz resonator in low to high subsonic flows and continuous to build an experimental database. This database is started as a backbone to be able to build a numerical model for aeroacoustic analysis for bleed geometries.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The main objective of this work is the experimental investigation of acoustic behavior of a Helmholtz resonator due to low to high subsonic flow across its opening.

The experimental measurements are performed in an open wind tunnel facility presented in [10]. A screw compressor delivers the air flow, which passes through a heat exchanger to regulate the required temperature. The flow is funneled through an orifice to measure the effective mass flow provided in the test section. This section of the wind tunnel incorporates a round settling chamber, and a rectangular channel. The channel decreases from a symmetrical cross section of 0.0625m^2 to a measurement channel of 100 mm width and 120 mm height. This contraction is performed in two steps by horizontally and vertically converging walls. The actual measurement channel consists of straight walls which all four can be dismantled for instrumentation and test objects. The temperature of the air flow is set at the start of the ramp up of the wind tunnel while pressure and mass flow are set with two valves upstream and downstream the test section, respectively, to reach the desired operating point.

In this campaign the hub of the measurement channel uses a main plate (length = 290 mm, width = 100 mm, thickness T) with a rectangular cut out of length L and width W as shown in FIGURE 1. The opening is centrally located between the two sidewalls of the measurement channel. The leading edge of this central opening is $3.125*L$ downstream the leading edge of the main plate.

A rectangular box with length of $3L$ and width W of $1.5L$ is used as cavity resonance volume. It is mounted symmetrically below the main plate. The inner corners of the box are rounded with radius $R = 0.15L$ to allow for a movable cavity bottom, shown in FIGURE 2. The cavity bottom has a thickness of $1.6*L$ to allow a stable movement of it within the resonator volume. O-rings around this plate are used as sealing against the rectangular resonator tube. The cavity bottom is connected to a stepper motor through a lead screw. This allows to change the resonator volume between $0.25 < L/D < 4$.

FIGURE 1: SCHEMATIC SIDE VIEW OF THE RESONATOR WITH KULITES AT THE NECK

FIGURE 2: SCHEMATIC TOP VIEW OF THE MOVEABLE CAVITY BOTTOM WITH KULITES IN THE CORNERS

Six Kulites are used to measure the unsteady pressures within the resonator to pick up amplifications. Four Kulites are symmetrically placed in all four corners of the moveable cavity bottom as shown in FIGURE 2 ($dx = dy = 0.175L$). Additionally, two Kulites are placed on the upstream and downstream wall of the cavity neck. The placement is in the center of the opening at $W/2$ and half the neck thickness T . The Kulite signal is recorded with a DTS SLICE PRO acquisition system connected with a Windows PC. During the measurements a sampling frequency of 25 kHz is used to record the signal.

TABLE 1: PRESSURE TRANSDUCER LOCATION FOR $L/D = 0.25$

Kulite	X	Y
1	Cavity wall LE	$0.5 T$
2	Cavity wall TE	$0.5 T$
3	Cavity bottom upstream	D
4	Cavity bottom upstream	D
5	Cavity bottom downstream	D
6	Cavity bottom downstream	D

A static pressure tap is placed at the side wall of the measurement channel. It is located at channel midspan centrally above the opening of the main plate. Additionally the total pressure is measured downstream of the settling chamber. These

values are acquired with a 16 channel pressure acquisition system averaged of 30 samples and at a frequency of 60 Hz in parallel. The sidewall pressure tap and the total pressure are used to set the operating point according to equation 1.

The test conditions at the inlet are set to total temperature of 30°C +/-0.5 K and a total pressure of 116.7 kPa (+/-0.3%). This is done for each measurement for better comparability. The operating points are in the range of Mach 0.3 and 0.8.

$$M = \left[\frac{2}{\gamma - 1} \times \left[\left(\frac{p_{tot,settling}}{p_{s,window}} \right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} - 1 \right] \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1)$$

The influence of humidity on the flow speed has been investigated by Wong [12]. It showed that for a worst case of 100 percent of relative humidity the change in the specific heat ratio is approximately 0.3%. For that case the speed of sound changes by 0.5 m/s. Therefore the humidity measurements from the test are disregarded for the following analysis.

One the other hand, the operating point is fixed and the cavity depth is changed by constantly moving the cavity bottom during the measurement. Three different moving speeds are used, but here only the results of the slowest plunger movement are shown. Furthermore the measurements are performed with an upward and downward movement of the cavity bottom to detect any possible lock-in resonances as described by Jones et al. [13]. During these experiments the Kulite signal is acquired continuously.

Windowing is used to split the time signal of the unsteady pressure measurements into equal parts. For each of these splits a fast Fourier transformation (FFT) is applied to the time signal and with the Fourier transform the power spectral density (PSD) is calculated

$$f = \frac{U(n-b)}{L\left(\frac{1}{K} + M\right)} \quad (2)$$

$$K = 0.57 - 0.66, b = 0.25, n = 1, 2, ..$$

$$f_{quarter} = \frac{c}{2l_{eff}} n \quad (3)$$

$$n = 1, 2, ..$$

$$f_{half} = \frac{c}{4l_{eff}} (2n - 1) \quad (4)$$

$$n = 1, 2, ..$$

$$f_{Helm} = \frac{n * c}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{A_{opening}}{V(l_{neck} + 2 * \delta_r)}} \quad (5)$$

$$n = 1, 2, ..$$

$$\delta_r = 1.7$$

Three theoretical models are used to predict resonance frequencies. Equation 2 represents the model developed by Rossiter [14] with the two empirical constants K and b that change depending on cavity depth. In the following figures the constant K is used in the range of 0.57 to 0.66. It has been suggested by Delprat [15] that for different L/D ratios the constants need to be changed to match experimental results best for the chosen range [16].

Equation 2 and equation 3 are representing quarter and half wavelength resonances. Cavity depth and test section height are identified by the quarter wavelength model. The cavity length resonance can be described with the half wavelength resonator model. The effective length in the equation is substituted with the equivalent geometrical length of either cavity length, test section height or cavity depth.

The last model used in this paper is the Helmholtz resonator model with a neck length correction defined by experimental results of Chanaud [17, 18]. He tested varies cavity geometries that resulted in specific numbers to adjust the neck length of the Helmholtz resonator according to the cavity opening.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the following figures the results of the measurements are shown. The focus is on Kulite 2 and Kulite 3. Kulite 2 is representative for all resonances in the whole operating range. Kulite 3 is chosen as representative for the Kulites in the cavity bottom since all four transducers show similar amplitudes in the picked-up resonances.

For each operating point resonances can be detected using the FFT when moving the cavity bottom without splitting the time signal shown in FIGURE 3. The pure time signal already gives an indication of critical length/depth ratios since the signal amplitude doubles at these regions. The results of the FFT of this signal can be seen in FIGURE 4. These computed frequencies do not occur during the whole measurement but rather in regions of certain depths. These initial results already classify critical regions in the operating range where resonances occur. However, the frequencies in FIGURE 4 don't give an indication of the cavity depth but rather the resonances with the highest amplitude for the chosen operating point.

FIGURE 3: CONTINUOUS KULITE SIGNAL OVER CHANGING CAVITY DEPTH AT MACH 0.6 FOR KULITE 2

FIGURE 4: FFT OF CONTINUOUS KULITE SIGNAL OVER CHANGING CAVITY DEPTH AT MACH 0.6 FOR KULITE 2

For more details the time signal is then evenly split around certain cavity depths. In order to identify a strong amplification of the resonance in the cavity the calculated PSD values are plotted as contour over a range of cavity depths and frequencies. This is done for the varying operating points. High amplitudes are colored in red and regions with low amplification are colored in blue. These results are obtained for each of the three speeds that are used to change the depth of the cavity. No difference in the location of amplitude peaks was noticeable between the different speeds (2.6sec/mm, 1.6sec/mm, 0.33sec/mm). However, the slower moving cavity bottom allowed for a better resolution of the picked-up frequencies over the range of measured cavity depths.

Some resonances are measured as horizontal lines which represent geometry induced resonances independent of change in depth.

3.1 Results per Operating point

FIGURE 5 and FIGURE 6 show the measurements at Mach 0.3. FIGURE 5 represents the flush mounted Kulite at the downstream wall of the cavity neck. A strong resonance appears around 1000 Hz around $L/D=1$ which follows the slope of the Helmholtz model. A weaker resonance around 1500Hz can be seen from $L/D=0.5$ to 0.25 . In FIGURE 6 the results for Kulite 3 at the cavity bottom are seen.

FIGURE 5: CONTOUR PLOT OF PSD FOR CONSTANT MACH NUMBER OF 0.3 FOR KULITE 2

The same resonances as in FIGURE 5 can be seen. However, the 1500Hz resonance has a larger amplitude around $L/D=0.33$. This frequency aligns well with the predicted cavity width model and indicates a quarter wavelength resonance.

FIGURE 6: CONTOUR PLOT OF PSD FOR CONSTANT MACH NUMBER OF 0.3 FOR KULITE 3

FIGURE 7 and FIGURE 8 show the measurements at Mach 0.4. Both Kulites pick up similar resonances with near equal amplification. However, the amplitudes from Kulite 3 at the cavity bottom are slightly higher similar to the results at Mach = 0.3. The strongest signal appear in the range of $L/D=0.29-0.25$. Here is a crossing of Rossiter 1 and Helmholtz models around 1300Hz.

The second resonance appears close to $L/D=0.33$ and is close to the cavity width prediction around 1600Hz.

The third resonance jumps in frequency to above 2300Hz at an L/D ratio around 0.4. Here the cavity depth and Helmholtz models intersect. The measurements seem to follow the curvature of the Helmholtz model.

A fourth weaker resonance appears between $L/D=2$ and 1. This is similar to the previous measurements at Mach = 0.3.

FIGURE 7: CONTOUR PLOT OF PSD FOR CONSTANT MACH NUMBER OF 0.4 FOR KULITE 2

FIGURE 9: CONTOUR PLOT OF PSD FOR CONSTANT MACH NUMBER OF 0.5 FOR KULITE 2

FIGURE 8: CONTOUR PLOT OF PSD FOR CONSTANT MACH NUMBER OF 0.4 FOR KULITE 3

FIGURE 10: CONTOUR PLOT OF PSD FOR CONSTANT MACH NUMBER OF 0.5 FOR KULITE 3

FIGURE 9 and FIGURE 10 represent the measurements from Kulite 2 and Kulite 3 and at Mach number of 0.5. Noticeable is that Kulite 2 at the cavity trailing edge wall show the higher amplitudes for the same resonances. The strongest signal appears between $L/D=0.4-0.33$ between 1500Hz and 1900Hz. This follows the trend of a Helmholtz harmonic. Additionally, around $L/D=0.33$ the signal intersects with the upper range of the Rossiter 1 mode at 1500Hz.

A second weaker resonance in the same L/D range appears between frequencies of 3220Hz and 3800Hz. This seems to be a harmonic of the first signal but follows the curvature of the cavity depth prediction.

A weak resonance can be measured in between cavity length and section height modes around 4500Hz for $L/D=2-0.5$ and around $L/D=0.29$.

The following figures concentrate on Kulite 2 at the cavity trailing edge wall since the analysis and the previous contour plots show that with increasing Mach number the results of the TE mounted sensor measured the highest amplified resonances and the same resonance appear for all Kulites.

FIGURE 11 shows the analyzed data from the downstream cavity wall neck sensor at Mach 0.6. Two high amplitude resonances are measured and match well with Helmholtz harmonics. The first resonance around $L/D=0.5-0.33$ matching with the Helmholtz prediction model between 1600Hz and 2300Hz. The second strong resonance appears around $L/D=0.29-0.25$ around 2500Hz. A third but weaker resonance matches well with the third harmonic of the cavity depth prediction for a depth around $L/D=0.4$ around 3800Hz. A weak resonance can be measured in between cavity length and section height modes around 4500Hz for $L/D=2-0.5$ and around $L/D=0.29$.

FIGURE 11: CONTOUR PLOT OF PSD FOR CONSTANT MACH NUMBER OF 0.6 FOR KULITE 2

FIGURE 12 represents the Kulite 2 signal for a Mach number of 0.7. The same resonances as for Mach number 0.6 appear. For the deepest cavity the resonance extends further towards $L/D=0.29$ at a frequency of 2500Hz. The second highest modes are measured for $L/D=0.6-0.38$ between 1800Hz and 3100Hz. A strong resonance over nearly the whole cavity depth range is recorded at 4300Hz. This resonance is well in the range of the Rossiter 2 mode. This resonance is interrupted exactly in the range of the first two modes.

FIGURE 12: CONTOUR PLOT OF PSD FOR CONSTANT MACH NUMBER OF 0.7 FOR KULITE 2

FIGURE 13 shows the measurements at Mach 0.8. for Kulite 2. The contour plot is similar to the one of Mach 0.7. However, the strongest signal is now measured around 4500Hz at the lower end of the Rossiter mode 2 range. This resonance is recorded over the whole L/D range with the exception of two sections around $L/D=0.67-0.5$ and $L/D=0.33-0.3$. For $L/D=0.67-0.5$ a resonance appears between 2200Hz and 3000Hz, starting at the upper end of Rossiter mode 1 and ending at a Helmholtz harmonic. It appears the mode is switching from one to the other.

For the range of $L/D=0.33-0.3$ the resonance is measured exactly between the predicted modes of cavity depth and Helmholtz.

FIGURE 13: CONTOUR PLOT OF PSD FOR CONSTANT MACH NUMBER OF 0.8 FOR KULITE 2

3.2 Discussion

The resonance behavior of a Helmholtz resonator with adjustable depth has been experimentally studied and the results compared to theoretical models.

The results show a dependency on flow speed and resonance behavior exists. For low subsonic Mach numbers of 0.3 geometric modes are measured over nearly the whole range of length to depth ratios. An increase to intermediate Mach numbers in the range of 0.4 to 0.6 moves the resonance peaks to deeper cavities below and L/D ratio of 0.5. In this flow speed range the theoretical prediction models correlate very well with the measurements. Rossiter 2 modes align well for high subsonic cases of Mach numbers bigger than 0.7. However, neither the quarter wavelength model nor the Helmholtz model fits the other resonance peaks measured in this operating range perfectly. Additionally, mode switching behavior seems to occur. Kegerise has shown this for a simple cavity at lower Mach numbers [16]. In order to match the measurement data for cases with Mach numbers higher than 0.5, the Helmholtz model needs adjustment. Panton had modified the Helmholtz model by adjusting the neck length further [19]. His model showed only major differences to the used Helmholtz model for shallower cavities with high L/D ratios. The Panton's and Chanaud's model converge to each other with decreasing L/D ratio (deeper cavities). The model by Panton shows how important geometry correction is since the slope of the curvature is slightly lower than the Helmholtz model. It has been disregarded in this paper since the highest deviation to the Helmholtz model is at higher L/D ratios.

The data shows that with increasing flow speed above Mach 0.5 a Helmholtz related resonance appears already at smaller volumes. A comparison with measurements of constant depth of the Helmholtz resonator and a sweep of the operating range could not be included here since not enough data has been obtained at the moment of publication of this article.

4. CONCLUSION

Helmholtz resonators have mostly been studied for lower flow speeds. The measurements in this study can be matched to the chosen analytical models up to intermediate subsonic flow speeds. Especially for low Mach number flows of 0.3 a geometrical dependency of cavity width is shown.

Further, the results indicate that for grazing flow speeds above Mach 0.5 the volume dependent resonances do not match the simple analytical models. In order to predict resonances at high subsonic speeds a correlation has to be developed from the acquired measurement data.

Furthermore, the results show a depth dependency to the flow speed. Resonances appear for a wider range of cavity volume for higher flow speeds.

An additional comparison to data for fixed depths of the used Helmholtz resonator could give a more conclusive picture of the resonance behavior at flow speeds above Mach 0.5.

The two main objectives in this project are numerical studies to match the experimental data. Second, experimentally study mitigation concepts for the measured resonances.

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